

Why should you do Research?

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Today, the world is facing pandemic outburst of diseases. Many Physicians-Scientist are working really hard to find out the measures which can either prevent or cure these diseases. But, we are still lagging behind in one or the other way. The most important way through which we will be able to curb these diseases is by doing Research. Research is defined as a process of investigation, interpretation and updating of the scientific knowledge [1].

Research is a tool for building knowledge and efficient learning. It is also important for budding and veteran writers, both offline and online. For those looking for a job or a promotion in good hospitals, research is likewise a necessity. It helps in understanding various ongoing health hazards. It is also a way to discard old hypothesis and develop new facts on which the medical world can completely rely on.

Research is the need of the day and everyone in medical profession is encouraged to do it including medical students. But their contribution to research is quite less when compared to students of other profession [2]. History says that many inventions were created by medical students. One of the most important research was of insulin discovery and its purification which was made by Dr. Frederick Banting and his second-year medical student assistant Charles Best [3]. Jay Mclean, a medical student from John Hopkins University had discovered Heparin [2]. However, Research should not be made compulsory [4].

Research entails both reading and writing. These two literacy functions help enable computation and comprehension. Reading opens the mind to a vast horizon of knowledge, while writing helps a reader use her/his own perspective and transform this into a more concrete idea that s/he understands. Apart from reading and writing, listening and speaking are also integral in conducting research. Interviews, attending knowledge-generating events, and casual talks with anyone certainly aid in formulating research topics. They can also facilitate the critical thinking process. Listening to experts discuss the merits of their studies helps the listener to analyze a certain issue and write about such analysis.

Curiosity may kill not just the cat, but the human as well. Yet, it is the same curiosity that fuels the mind to seek for answers. Indeed, research and doing research encourage people to explore possibilities, to understand existing disorders, and to disclose facts. Without research, healthy life would remain as fantasy. Reading, writing, observing, analyzing, and interacting with others facilitate an inquisitive mind's quest for knowledge and efficient learning. Research serves as an instrument to achieve that healthy world goal.

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